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Research Article

**PERSPECTIVES AND KNOWLEDGE REGARDING ADDICTS,
THEIR VIOLENT BEHAVIOR AND ROLE AS A PARENT**Sana Saeed¹¹PhD Pharmacology scholar, Department of Pharmacy, The University of Faisalabad.

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Abstract:*Objective: To identify the perspectives and knowledge regarding addicts, their violent behavior and role a parent.**Material and methods: the cross-sectional study was conducted. Participants were given Likert scale questionnaire. 264 participants participated actively and gave proper response to the questionnaire. Demographic data was collected which showed diversity. obtained results were interpreted into data form and analyzed by SPSS software. The mean and standard deviation were obtained. The data also subjected to Pearson's correlation to find out association between responses.**Results: 97.7 % Participants strongly agreed that addicts indulge to verbal and physical abuse more frequently. They also established a perfect association between drug addiction and narcissistic patterns and bipolar streaks 70.8% and 73.1% respectively. Participant disagreed that addicts can fulfil their marital and parental responsibilities in an effective way 76.8% and 86.4% respectively.**Discussion/conclusion: the study throws a light on insights that govern on the minds of people regarding drug abuser and outcomes of substance use. A drug addict has multifocal effects on family and people around them. . It's a high time to mitigate the impacts of substance usage and be a moral support to drug abusers so that they can rehabilitate themselves and impact other's lives in a most productive way.***Key Words:** Drug addiction, Substance abuse, violence, parental role**Corresponding author:****Sana Saeed,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Globally, the 11.8 million mortalities are caused by drug addiction or a substance use disorder each year, which incorporates drinking alcohol, smoking, and using illegal drugs.¹ By definition, drug addiction is a chronic, relapsing disorder brought on by the lasting effects of substances on the brain. Drug addiction is intertwined with social and behavioral components that are equally notable aspects of the condition, similar to other neuropsychiatric disorders, complicating the entire therapeutic option.² In U.S, over than 8.3 million kids under the age of 18 (11.9%) lived with at least one parent who was abusing alcohol or illegal drugs or was dependent on them.³ Substance use issues or drug dependence are

frequently regarded as family diseases. A comprehensive and trustworthy body of evidence has established a connection between parental drug addiction and a higher risk of substance use in their offspring at the time of adulthood, as teenage drug user, and other undesirable consequences, such juvenile misconduct and behavior problems.⁴ Children who live in settings where one or both parents deal with drug abuse may suffer negative effects as a result of the distressing, volatile, and unpredictable circumstances in which these families frequently function.⁵ There are many ways that substance abuser or a drug addict can impact the family as shown in figure.1.

Figure.1: Multifocal approach how a drug addict impacts family

There is a strong correlation between substance use and domestic violence. Domestic violence can occur in various ways over time, including physical, sexual, and psychological abuse. Such aggression may take the form of assaulting the spouse when intoxicated.⁶ This is also linked to children's higher levels of disruptive conduct, aggressive behavior disorders, diminished social skills, early initiation of a drug use, interpersonal conflict, and poor self-control. Both externalizing conditions like schizophrenia and internalizing disorders like anxiety

and depression have been attributed to parental drug use.⁷ According to the American Psychiatric Association, among other prerequisites for the diagnosis of drug addiction are repeated drug usage that leads to renouncing significant responsibilities at work, college, or household (evaluation criteria 5), prolong substance abuse despite possessing sustained or repetitive interpersonal or social problems triggered or worsened by the consequences of the drug use (evaluation criterion 6) and frequent substance use in physically risky

situations (criterion 8). According to these criteria, drug use disorders share two similar traits: (a) a lack of drive to limit or stop usage when it results in pain for family and friends or other nearest and dearest; and (b) a refusal of risk to one's person in several ways, such as health risks and legal repercussions.⁸ Drug usage has been linked to extreme narcissism because those who exhibit it involve in more egocentric and reprehensible behavior, reap the benefits of others, are unable to recognize their mistakes, and are motivated by incentives.⁹

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among people from various walks of life. A LIKERT Scale Questionnaire was utilized to assess the perspectives and knowledge regarding addicts, their violent behavior and role as a parent. 264 people

responded in this study and gave their opinions through questionnaire. Then these responses were analyzed for correlation, thus Pearson's Coefficient. Questionnaire was based on the tendency of addicts to develop violent behavior including both verbal and physical, narcissism, extreme temper, effect of addiction on their financial status, marital status and impact on their children as a parent. Questionnaire was based on responses in Likert scale: strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree. Every participant was narrated with purpose of the study and consented to the fill the questionnaire.

RESULTS:

Results obtained were compiled into data and analyzed by employing SPSS software. The details of the participants related to their demographic were obtained. These are given in table.no.1.

Age	18-25 years N (%)	26-33 years N (%)	33-40 years N (%)
Gender			
Male	87 (84.5)	36 (40)	49 (68)
female	16 (15.5)	53 (60)	23 (32)
Education			
Matriculation	25 (24.3)	3 (3.37)	7 (10)
Intermediate	45 (43.7)	13 (14.6)	15 (20.1)
Graduation	33 (32)	41 (46.1)	29 (40.2)
Master	0	32 (36)	21 (29.2)
Marital status			
Married	31 (30.1)	66 (74.2)	59 (82)
unmarried	72 (69.9)	23 (25.8)	13 (18)
Employment status			
Employed	49 (48)	71 (80)	64 (89)
Unemployed	54 (52)	18 (20)	8 (11)

The participants were divided into categories of age groups 18-25 years, 26-33 years and 34-40 years. 72.4%, 88.3% and 97.7% participants strongly agreed that there is a common link between addiction and verbal abuse, physical abuse and both respectively. 70.8% strongly agreed that addicts show narcissistic pattern in their personality. 73.1 % strongly agreed that there is presence of extreme of emotional disturbances in addicts. 76.8% strongly disagreed with that addicts are able to maintain their marital responsibilities. 80.7 % strongly disagreed that addicts can be economically independent. 86% strongly disagreed that addict can be a good parent. 88.3% strongly agreed with the fact that addicts have a tendency to precipitate substance abuse in their children. 86.4% strongly agreed that an addict as a parent can increase the chances of development of juvenile misconduct in his children. Details of study are summarized in table.no.2 and figure.no.1.

	Strongly agree N (%)	Agree N (%)	Neutral N (%)	Disagree N (%)	Strongly disagree N (%)
1. Do you think Verbal abuse is common among addicts?	191 (72.4)	71(26.9)	2 (0.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)
2. Do you think physical abuse is common in addicts?	233 (88.3)	27 (10.2)	4 (1.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)
3. Do addicts demonstrate both verbal and physical abuse?	258 (97.7)	5 (1.9)	1 (0.4)	0 (0)	0 (0)
4. Do you think Narcissistic patterns are present in addicts?	187 (70.8)	51 (19.3)	6 (2.3)	11 (4.2)	9 (3.4)
5. Do addicts have extremes of emotional disturbances?	193 (73.1)	54 (20.4)	5 (1.9)	8 (3.0)	4 (1.5)
6. Do you think addicts are able to maintain marital responsibilities?	3 (1.1)	5 (1.9)	1 (0.4)	52 (19.7)	203 (76.8)
7. Do you reckon that addicts can be economically independent?	0 (0)	1 (0.4)	2 (0.8)	48 (18.2)	213 (80.7)
8. Do you think addicts can be a good parent if married?	0 (0)	4 (1.5)	1 (0.4)	32 (12.1)	227 (86.0)
9. Can addict parent precipitate substance abuse in his children?	232 (88.3)	28 (10.2)	1 (0.4)	3 (1.1)	0 (0)
10. Can an addict parent increase the chances of development of juvenile misconduct in his children?	228 (86.4)	31 (11.7)	3 (1.1)	2 (0.8)	0 (0)

There Mean \pm SD against each response is given in table.no.3. Pearson's correlation coefficient depicted Strong positive association ($r=1$) between those who strongly agreed that male addicts show verbal and physical abuse also strongly agree that addicts tend to have narcissistic and extreme emotional disturbances. Similarly strong positive association ($r=1$) was found between those who strongly disagree that addict can take marital and financial responsibilities ,also strongly agreed on the fact that addicts cannot fulfill their role as a parent. They were found to strongly agree with the that an addict could encourage their children to substance use and indulged them in juvenile misconducts, thus hampering their well-being.

	Mean \pm SD
1. Do you think Verbal abuse is common among male addicts?	4.72 \pm 0.47
2. Do you think physical abuse is common in male addicts?	4.87 \pm 0.38
3. Do male addicts demonstrate both verbal and physical abuse?	4.97 \pm 0.18
4. Do you think Narcissistic patterns are present in male addicts?	4.50 \pm 0.97
5. Do male addicts have extremes of emotional disturbances?	4.61 \pm 0.80
6. Do you think male addicts are able to maintain marital responsibilities?	1.31 \pm 0.69
7. Do you reckon that male addicts can be economically independent?	1.21 \pm 0.45
8. Do you think male addicts can be a good parent (father) if married?	1.17 \pm 0.49
9. Can male addict parent precipitate substance abuse in his children?	4.86 \pm 0.45
10. Can a male addict parent increase the chances of development of juvenile misconduct in his children?	4.84 \pm 0.45

Figure.1: Perspectives and knowledge regarding addicts, their violent behavior and role as a parent

DISCUSSION:

This study adds to the substantial studies examining the relationship between usage of psychoactive substances and violent conduct in individuals. Our survey supports this viewpoint because 72.4% (4.72 ± 0.47) of respondents strongly believed that drug addiction or substance use results in abusive conduct in individuals who engage in such activities.¹⁰ Behavioral disorders, past drug use problems, as well as a few mood and anxiety disorders, all showed very significant and persistent connections. This survey found that 70.8% (4.50 ± 0.97) and 73.1% (4.61 ± 0.80) of respondents strongly agreed that drug users display excessive mood swings and narcissism, respectively.¹¹ Without taking into account the effects on the entire family, drug users cannot be understood or treated properly. Researchers in addictions have verified the bidirectional correlation between the environment and the condition of addiction. Everyone has an impact on their social surroundings and is also affected by it. It is three times more probable for a parent who uses drugs to harm their child physically or sexually. According to this survey, 97.7% (4.97 ± 0.18) of respondents strongly believe that addicts cause verbal and physical harm to their family and others around them. As a result, these kids have a 40% increased risk of committing a violent offense and a 50% increased risk of being arrested as minors. 86.4% (4.84 ± 0.45) people strongly agree that maltreatment through a substance abuser effect children and make

them more vulnerable towards juvenile misconduct. Children who have suffered abuse are more prone to exhibit behavioral issues, conduct difficulties, and other borderline personality disorders, whereas children who have experienced maltreatment are more likely to exhibit anxiety - related disorders (depression, social withdrawal).¹² Similar to this, drug use and a number of indices of poor psychological health are substantially correlated with hostile attitude towards partners. According to studies there are significant disparities between drug-addicted individuals with and without experiences of relationship violence. 76.8% (1.31 ± 0.69) participant in this study strongly disagreed with the societal notion that drug addict can fulfill the marital responsibilities. Particularly, people who suffered violence from drug-dependent Partner exhibit more psychopathological symptoms and personality abnormalities than non-addicted individuals.¹³

CONCLUSION:

Henceforth, this study has depicted how drug addict imposes multifocal effect on the lives of family and the related people. The study has also shown how the society is crystal clear regarding the addicts or substance abusers, how much this is associated with the wellbeing of children and families and abnormal personality patterns consequential of substance use. It's a high time to mitigate the impacts of substance usage and be a moral support to drug abusers so that

they can rehabilitate themselves and impact other's lives in a most productive way.

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Data Availability: All data generated or analyzed during this study is included in this article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

Ethical issues: Written and informed consent has been taken from participants for publishing their perspectives.

REFERENCES:

- Roth GA, Abate D, Abate KH, Abay SM, Abbafati C, Abbasi N, et al. Global, regional, and national age-sex-specific mortality for 282 causes of death in 195 countries and territories, 1980–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *Lancet*. 2018;392:1736–88.
- Cheron, J., Kerchove d'Exaerde, A.d. Drug addiction: from bench to bedside. *Transl Psychiatry* **11**, 424 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41398-021-01542-0>
- Abuse, S. (2009). The NSDUH report: Children living with substance-dependent or substance-abusing parents: 2002 to 2007.
- Rhee, S. H., Hewitt, J. K., Young, S. E., Corley, R. P., Crowley, T. J., & Stallings, M. C. (2003). Genetic and environmental influences on substance initiation, use, and problem use in adolescents. *Archives of general psychiatry*, *60*(12), 1256-1264.
- Kumpfer, K. L., & Bluth, B. (2004). Parent/child transactional processes predictive of resilience or vulnerability to "substance abuse disorders". *Substance use & misuse*, *39*(5), 671-698.
- Foran HM, O'Leary KD. Alcohol and intimate partner violence: A meta-analytic review. *Clin Psychol Rev* 2008;28:1222-34
- Leonard KE, Eiden RD. Marital and family processes in the context of alcohol use and alcohol disorders. *Annu Rev Clin Psychol* 2007;3:285-310
- Salazar, J., Page, B., & Ripoll, C. (2021). Features, state and context of narcissism in drug misuse. *Substance use & misuse*, *56*(1), 11-24.
- Mowlaie, M., Abolghasemi, A., & Aghababaei, N. (2016). Pathological narcissism, brain behavioral systems and tendency to substance abuse: The mediating role of self-control. *Personality and Individual Differences*, *88*, 247-250.
- Kim, J.H.; Hahlweg, K.; Schulz, W. Early childhood parenting and adolescent bullying behavior: Evidence from a randomized intervention at ten-year follow-up. *Soc. Sci. Med.* **2021**, *282*, 114114.
- Swendsen, J., Conway, K. P., Degenhardt, L., Glantz, M., Jin, R., Merikangas, K. R., ... & Kessler, R. C. (2010). Mental disorders as risk factors for substance use, abuse and dependence: results from the 10-year follow-up of the National Comorbidity Survey. *Addiction*, *105*(6), 1117-1128.
- Lander, Laura; Howsare, Janie; Byrne, Marilyn (2013). *The Impact of Substance Use Disorders on Families and Children: From Theory to Practice. Social Work in Public Health*, *28*(3-4), 194–205. doi:10.1080/19371918.2013.759005
- Arteaga, A., Fernández-Montalvo, J., & López-Goñi, J. J. (2012). Diferencias en variables de personalidad en sujetos adictos a drogas con y sin conductas violentas contra la pareja. *Acción psicológica*, *9*(1), 19-31.